

Prevalence of Early Childhood Caries and Associated Risk Factors among 3-6 Years Old Children of Delhi-NCR: Cross-Sectional Study**Padamja Katiyar¹, Pramod Kumar², Muhamad Nishad Thayath³**¹MDS, Department of Preventive and Pediatric Dentistry, Shree Bankey Bihari Dental College & Research Centre, NH-24, Masuri, Ghaziabad (UP)²Senior Resident, Department of Dentistry, Jawaharlal Nehru Medical College and Hospital, Bhagalpur, Bihar³Professor and Head, Department of Preventive and Pediatric Dentistry, Shree Bankey Bihari Dental College & Research Centre, NH-24, Masuri, Ghaziabad (UP)

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Corresponding Author: Dr. Padamja Katiyar

Conflict of interest: Nil

Abstract:**Background:** Oral health issues and diseases can have a negative impact on a child's overall health and development as well as their quality of life. While having healthy teeth is not the only aspect of having good oral health, uncontrolled and active caries is a major cause of poor oral and general health in many children. The aim of the present study was to find the prevalence of Early Childhood Caries and associated risk factors among 3-6 years preschools children in Delhi/NCR.**Methods:** The present study was carried out in Department of Pediatrics Dentistry, Shree Bankey Bihari Dental College and Research Centre, Masuri, Ghaziabad. This descriptive cross-sectional study was based upon oral examination of children of study population with parent's perception on the basis of questionnaire. This study was conducted in the various preschools taking care of children in Delhi/NCR randomly and in the Department of Preventive and Paediatrics Dentistry of Shree Bankey Bihari Dental College, Masuri, Ghaziabad.**Results:** Four region Delhi, Ghaziabad, Noida and Greater Noida comprising of 500 children from different preschools in each region were selected, total of 2000 children were examined out of which 1072 were male and 928 were females. Among them, 2.02 mean age, 560 were caries active and 1440 were caries free. Overall ECC prevalence was 28% with highest prevalence in Greater Noida and Noida which have similar value and least prevalence was found in Delhi (11%). Mean def value was found to be 2.02 and Mean DMFT 0.13 respectively. The difference in the prevalence of ECC was found between different age groups, highest value of 32.7% at age group 3 years, 4 years 28.2% followed by equal distribution in age group 4 and 6 years to be 25%. The difference between the age group was not significant. The caries prevalence was more in females as compared with males.**Conclusion:** Epidemiology of any disease is a very helpful tool to assess the actual status of the disease among population. Diversity in population of India with respect to dental caries provides a very beautiful condition for the study of different factors associated with dental caries. However this work is a small effort towards understanding of factors associated with dental caries, but this study fails to correlate the data with other studies in this study sample population.**Keywords:** Childhood Caries, Delhi/NCR, Paediatrics Dentistry.This is an Open Access article that uses a funding model which does not charge readers or their institutions for access and distributed under the terms of the Creative Commons Attribution License (<http://creativecommons.org/licenses/by/4.0>) and the Budapest Open Access Initiative (<http://www.budapestopenaccessinitiative.org/read>), which permit unrestricted use, distribution, and reproduction in any medium, provided original work is properly credited.**Introduction**

Oral health is one component of general health and is an important factor in the normal development of a child and its general health and can adversely affect quality of life. [1]

Oral health problems or illnesses can influence the general development of a child and its general health and can adversely quality of life. [2] Although enjoying oral health includes more than just having healthy teeth, many children have inadequate oral and general health because of uncon-

trolled and active caries. [1] Voluminous dental literature exists about caries levels in the population. These data have been obtained from the major cities and cosmopolitan areas. The overall impression is that dental caries has increased in prevalence and severity in the urban and cosmopolitan population over the last couples of decades. [3]

Dental Caries is a disease with multi factorial causes. The prevalence and incidence of dental caries in a population is influenced by a number of risk fac-

tors. [4] It is considered as an ancient disease dating back to the time that agriculture replaced hunting and gathering as the principle source of food, although the prevalence and severity was much lower than what we see today. [5] Dental Caries can be traced as old civilization with its evidence seen even in skeletal remnants of prehistoric humans. According to World Health Organization (WHO) it is next to the common cold in children. [1] Children suffer from much infectious disease during the first three years of life around the time of eruption of the deciduous teeth. Parents do not give sufficient attention to prevent the occurrence of these at early age. The Early childhood caries which is combination of child being infected with bacteria and sugar indigestion is one of the disease. It has been a major health problem over years and still continues today affecting the physical growth and development, as well as the social adaptation of young children. The dental health of preschool child has not been clearly documented to the same extent as the dental health of school children. [7]

ECC is a rampant chronic, transmissible infectious disease, which can destroy the primary dentition of toddlers and young children. [8] The American Academy of Pediatric Dentistry (AAPD) in 2003 defines ECC as the presence of one or more decayed (non cavitated or cavitated), missing (due to caries), or filled tooth surfaces in any primary tooth in a child upto 71 months of age or younger. The academy also specifies that, in children younger than 3 years of age, any sign of smooth surface caries is indicative of severe early childhood caries (S-ECC). From ages 3 through 5, 1 or more cavitated, missing (due to caries) or filled smooth surfaces in primary maxillary anterior teeth or decayed, missing, or filled score of ≥ 4 (age 3), or ≥ 5 (age 4), or ≥ 6 (age 5) surfaces constitutes S-ECC. [9]

Despite improvement over several decades oral disease among the children remains a serious problem. During past decades the common consensus from many reports worldwide was that the caries had decline in population significantly and was continuing to decline in populations but current review of the available epidemiological data from many countries clearly indicates that there is marked increase in prevalence of dental caries. The dental community has prided itself on efforts that have reduced Dental Caries including use of various components and diet and health education. But still there is "global increase in Dental Caries" among toddlers and young children. [10]

There are so many studies been conducted worldwide to find the prevalence of ECC and associated risk factors but there is scarcity of any such literature in this region of Delhi/NCR which indeed requires more attention and hence no literature focus light on prevalence of caries in children of Delhi

and National Capital Regions despite of so much data worldwide on dental caries.

Aim and Objectives

Aim: The aim of the present study was to find the prevalence of Early Childhood Caries and associated risk factors among 3-6 years preschools children in Delhi/NCR.

Objectives:

- To find the prevalence of ECC among 3-6 year old preschools children of Delhi/NCR.
- To find the Oral Hygiene Status among 3-6 year old preschools children of Delhi/NCR.
- To compare the parental assessment with def/DMFT score.

Materials and Methods

The present study was carried out in Department of Pediatrics Dentistry, Shree Bankey Bihari Dental College and Research Centre, Masuri, Ghaziabad.

Study Design and Location

This descriptive cross-sectional study was based upon oral examination of children of study population with parent's perception on the basis of questionnaire. This study was conducted in the various preschools taking care of children in Delhi/NCR randomly and in the Department of Preventive and Paediatrics Dentistry of Shree Bankey Bihari Dental College, Masuri, Ghaziabad.

Ethics approval and consent form

Ethics approval for the study was obtained from ethical committee of Shree Bankey Bihari Dental College and Research Centre, Masuri, Ghaziabad. Each school or organization was asked to review the consent form outlining the purpose of the study and its procedures, before beginning the study. A simplified report of the child's health according to the findings of the conducted examination was provided upon request.

Training and calibration of examiner

The clinical examination was carried out by single trained and calibrated examiner to ensure consistent recording and clinical judgments for reliable valid data collection.

Study subjects

2000 preschools children were included in the study with prior consent from the concerned school or hospital authority. Children aged between 3-6 years old were selected. Parent-Caregiver of same children were given a Parent-Caregiver Perception Questionnaire to fill either in Parent Teacher meetings or attached to school diary and collected later on. Subjects were divided on the basis of regions.

- Ghaziabad

- Delhi
- Greater noida
- Noida

Subjects Inclusion criteria

- Age: 3-6 years
- Gender: male/female
- Socio-economic status: Varied
- Children/parent/caregivers willing to participate in study.

Subjects Exclusion criteria

- Medically compromised
- Handicapped children
- Congenital defects
- Not able to give consent

Study Armamentarium/Materials

The following instruments and supplies in sufficient number were used:

1. Plain mouth mirrors
2. Explorers
3. Tweezers
4. Kidney trays
5. Gloves and mouth masks
6. Cotton rolls
7. Cloth hand towels
8. Savlon solution: (chlorhexidine solution i.p. 1.5% v/v and strong cetrimide solution b.p. equivalent to i.p. 3.0% v/w, colors: Tetrazine and Sunset Yellow FCF).
9. Modified oral assessment form was designed on the basis of WHO Oral Health Assessment Form – 5th ed. 2013.
10. def/DMFT recording form was used to calculate decayed teeth in the children.
11. Parent/ Caregivers Perceptions Questionnaires (KAP) – Fifteen multiple choice questions were developed on review of the relevant literature which cover equal distribution of five questions of knowledge, Practice and Attitude of Parent/Caregivers on their child oral health other barriers to obtaining dental services and caregivers socio demographic information.

Study Methodology

An epidemiological cross-sectional study among 2000 children was conducted to assess the prevalence of dental caries and associated risk factors among 3-6-year-old preschools children of Delhi/NCR.

Sample Selection

The sample size was selected to be 2000. Permission to conduct the survey in the selected schools was obtained from the respective authorities. Informed consent was obtained from the school authorities and parent /Caregiver. This study was reviewed and cleared by the Ethics Committee of

Shree Bankey Bihari Dental College and Research Centre, Ghaziabad.

Method of sampling

To assume homogeneity of the sample the map of Delhi /NCR was procured and the city was arbitrarily divided into different zones. The education Department of Municipal Corporation was approached to collect the information of schools functioning in each zone. Permission was obtained from the concerned authorities like, Headmaster, Research and Ethical Committee of Shree Bankey Bihari Dental College and Research Institute, Ghaziabad India before examining of children. Thus, out of four zones a total of 2000 pre-school going children were examined.

Study area

The field practice area of Delhi/NCR forms the study area. The different pre-schools/ schools from Delhi, Ghaziabad, Noida, Greater Noida were included. There were around 500 children included from each region randomly selected schools of each region to maintain the homogeneity of sample.

Details of examination

The clinical examination of all pre-schools children was entirely done by a single investigator. Before conducting the survey, the investigator was calibrated at Department of Pedodontics and Preventive Dentistry, Shree Bankey Bihari Dental College and Research Centre, Ghaziabad under the guidance of a professor in order to limit examiner variability. Re-examinations were carried out on approximately one in ten children selected at random to have a constant check on the inter examiner variability. Parents were requested to fill this form giving details of the diet, which the subject had consumed over the past one day to assess the KAP among the group.

The knowledge attitude and practice of these schools children and their parents with regard to oral health measures was recorded on a specially designed computerized proforma to correlate the existing dental caries status with various risk factors.

Clinical examination

A type III (using mouth mirror and explorer with proper illumination) examination was carried out under adequate illumination using plane mouth.

Clinical conditions recorded were caries in primary dentition of 3-5-year-old by decayed, extracted, filled teeth (deft) and oral hygiene status was also assessed by OHI-S index. Each child was examined on an ordinary upright chair with the help of mouth mirror in an adequate natural light. Prior to examination, the child was asked to rinse the mouth thor-

oughly. The teeth were then cleaned and dried with cotton roll to eliminate confusing effects of food debris and saliva. The examination was done by one examiner only to eliminate error. It was carried out in the uniform manner, starting from the most posterior tooth in maxillary right quadrant and then in a clockwise direction. Recording criteria for dental caries. The def index for primary dentition was introduced by Klein, Palmer, Knutson in 1938 and modified by WHO: 1. DMF which measures the prevalence of dental caries/Teeth. The dental caries was assessed as per the WHO criteria (1997) and def, decayed, missing, filled surfaces index for primary teeth.

The data was recorded on modified WHO oral health assessment form (1997). Children of 1-2 pre-schools were examined every day.

Calculation: def for primary dentition

Information can be calculated from the information of WHO dentition status and treatment needs. a) The d-component includes all teeth with codes 1 (B) or 2 (C). b) The m-component comprises teeth coded 4 (E) that is, missing due to caries c) The f-component includes teeth with code 3 (D) filled with no decay.

Recording criteria for oral hygiene index

The OHI was developed in 1960 by John C. Greene and Jack R. Vermillion to classify and assess oral hygiene status. Even though, the OHI was determined to be simple and sensitive, it was time consuming and required more decision making.

Hence, an effort was made to develop a more simplified version with equal sensitivity. However, the criteria and scoring for the tooth surface. Surface and teeth to be examined:

- 16 - Upper right first molar, buccal.
- 51/11- upper right central incisor, labial.
- 26 - Upper left first molar, buccal.
- 36 - lower left first molar, lingual
- 71/31- lower left first central incisor, labial.
- 46 - Lower right first molar, lingual.

Examination method and scoring system

The surface area of the debris is examined by running the side of explorer along the tooth surface being examined. The occlusal or incisal extent of debris is noted as it is removed.

Score Criteria

- 0 No debris or stains present
- 1 Soft debris covering not more than 1/3rd of the tooth surface or presence of extrinsic stains

without other debris regardless of surface covered.

- 2 Soft debris covering more than 1/3rd but not more than 2/3rd of the exposed tooth surface.
- 3 Soft debris covering more than 2/3rd of the exposed tooth surface.

Calculation of DI = Total score/number of surfaces examined the oral hygiene examination and scoring for DI always should precede the oral examination and scoring for calculus index (CI).

Calculus index

There are basically two main types of dental calculus, which are differentiated primarily by location on the tooth in relation to free gingival margin. a. Supra-gingival calculus. b. Sub-gingival calculus.

Score

- 0 No debris or calculus present.
- 1 Supra-gingival calculus covering not more than 1/3rd of the exposed tooth surface.
- 2 Supra-gingival calculus covering more than 1/3rd but not more than 2/3rd of the exposed tooth surface or presence of individual flecks of sub-gingival calculus around the cervical portion of the tooth or both.
- 3 Supra-gingival calculus covering more than 2/3rd of the exposed tooth surface or a continuous heavy band of subgingiva calculus.

Calculation of CI = Total score/number of surfaces examined.

Calculation of oral hygiene Simplified index

Once the debris index-simplified (DI) and CI (CI) are calculated separately then, they are added together to get the OHI score. $OHI-S = DI(S) + CI(S)$

Score Criteria

- 0 Excellent
- 0.1-1.2 Good
- 1.3-3 Fair
- 3.1-6 Poor

Statistical Analysis

Data was recorded in an MS Office Excel sheet using patient identification number, age, and sex according to different regions.

Data entry and descriptive statistical analysis were performed using SPSS Version 20. By employing suitable statistical tests the association between study variables was analysed with level of significance established at $p \leq 0.05$ at 95% CI.

Results

Table 1: Comparison of four regions on basis of def, DMFT and ECC

		Regions					Chi-square value	p-value
		Ghaziabad	Delhi	Noida	Greater Noida	Total		
deft prevalence	Present	99	53	200	193	545	248.171	<0.001*
		19.8%	10.6%	40.0%	38.6%	27.3%		
DMFT prevalence	Present	3	2	6	5	16	4.697	0.041*
		0.6%	0.4%	1.2%	1.0%	0.8%		
ECC	Present	99	55	205	201	560	247.647	<0.001*
		19.8%	11.0%	40.4%	40.2%	28.0%		

Chi-square test, *Significant difference

Table 2: Comparison of def, DMFT and ECC on basis Gender: Overall study population

		Sex		Total	Chi-square value	p-value
		Male	Female			
deft prevalence	Absent	794	661	1,455	2.059	0.151
		74.1%	71.2%	72.8%		
	Present	278	267	545		
		25.9%	28.8%	27.3%		
DMFT prevalence	Absent	1,049	910	1,959	0.105	0.746
		97.9%	98.1%	98.0%		
	Present	23	18	41		
		2.1%	1.9%	2.1%		
ECC	Absent	785	655	1,440	1.760	0.185
		73.2%	70.6%	72.0%		
	Present	287	273	560		
		26.8%	29.4%	28.0%		

Chi-square test, #Non-significant difference

Table 3: OHI-S Overall (Regions)

OHI-s	Regions					Chi-square value	p-value
	Ghaziabad	Delhi	Noida	Greater Noida	Total		
Good	308	334	293	297	1,232	39.548	<0.001*
	61.6%	66.8%	58.6%	59.4%	61.6%		
Fair	139	135	119	118	511		
	27.8%	27.0%	23.8%	23.6%	25.6%		
Poor	53	31	88	85	257		
	10.6%	6.2%	17.6%	17.0%	12.9%		
Total	500	500	500	500	2,000		
	100.0%	100.0%	100.0%	100.0%	100.0%		

Chi-square test, *Significant difference

Table 4: OHI-S correlation between four regions

Regions	Regions	OHI-S	
		Mean Difference	p-value
Ghaziabad	Delhi	0.17	0.194
Ghaziabad	Noida	-0.26	0.001*
Ghaziabad	Greater Noida	-0.35	<0.001*
Delhi	Noida	-0.43	<0.001*
Delhi	Greater Noida	-0.52	<0.001*
Noida	Greater Noida	-0.09	0.198

Post-hoc Bonferroni test, *Significant difference

Table 5: deft mean: On basis of four regions

	deft				
	Number	Mean	Std.Deviation	F-value	p-value
Ghaziabad	500	1.89	2.05	6.300	<0.001*
Delhi	500	1.55	2.97		
Noida	500	2.25	2.30		
Greater Noida	500	2.38	2.30		
Total	2000	2.02	2.41		

One-way ANOVA test, *Significant difference

Table 6: Mean DMFT among Four Regions

	DMFT				
	Number	Mean	Std.Deviation	F-value	p-value
Ghaziabad	500	0.12	0.45	7.904	<0.001*
Delhi	500	0.10	0.25		
Noida	500	0.15	0.85		
Greater Noida	500	0.15	0.97		
Total	2000	0.13	0.63		

One-way ANOVA test, *Significant difference

Table 7: ECC mean-Interregion

	ECC				
	Number	Mean	Std.Deviation	F-value	p-value
Ghaziabad	500	1.99	2.05	6.388	<0.001*
Delhi	500	1.67	2.97		
Noida	500	2.40	2.30		
Greater Noida	500	2.47	2.30		
Total	2000	2.13	2.41		

One-way ANOVA test, *Significant difference

Table 8: ECC Mean interregional comparison

Regions	Regions	ECC	
		Mean Difference	p-value
Ghaziabad	Delhi	0.32	0.049*
Ghaziabad	Noida	-0.41	0.005*
Ghaziabad	Greater Noida	-0.48	<0.001*
Delhi	Noida	-0.73	<0.001*
Delhi	Greater Noida	-0.80	<0.001*
Noida	Greater Noida	-0.07	0.854

Post-hoc Bonferroni test, *Significant difference

Table 9: ECC correlation with region

Regions	Regions	ECC	
		Mean Difference	p-value
3years	4years	0.66	0.049*
	5years	1.02	0.005*
	6years	1.48	<0.001*
4years	3years	-0.66	0.049
	5years	0.36	<0.001*
	6years	0.82	<0.001*
5years	3years	-1.02	0.005
	4years	-0.36	<0.001*
	6years	0.46	0.854

Post-hoc bonferroni test, *Significant difference

Table 10: KAP Correlation with def and DMFT

Knowledge score	Pearson Correlation	deft	ECC
		P-value	<0.001**
	Number	2000	2000
Attitude score	Pearson Correlation	0.323	0.317
	P-value	<0.001**	<0.001**
	Number	2000	2000
Practice score	Pearson Correlation	0.445	0.445
	P-value	<0.001**	<0.001**
	Number	2000	2000
Total score	Pearson Correlation	0.367	0.372
	P-value	<0.001**	<0.001**
	Number	2000	2000

Pearson Correlation test, **Correlation is significant at the 0.01 level (2-tailed).

Summary

This present study was undertaken to find prevalence of ECC and associated risk factors among age group 3-6years children of Delhi /NCR. Four region Delhi, Ghaziabad, Noida and Greater Noida comprising of 500 children from different pre-schools in each region were selected, total of 2000 children were examined out of which 1072 were male and 928 were females. Among them, 2.02 mean age, 560 were caries active and 1440 were caries free.

Overall ECC prevalence was 28% with highest prevalence in Greater Noida and Noida which have similar value and least prevalence was found in Delhi (11%). Mean def value was found to be 2.02 and Mean DMFT 0.13 respectively. The difference in the prevalence of ECC was found between different age groups, highest value of 32.7% at age group 3 years, 4 years 28.2% followed by equal distribution in age group 4 and 6 years to be 25%. The difference between the age group was not significant. The caries prevalence was more in females as compared with males.

OHI-S overall in study population was 61.6% were good. Comparison among different regions found that Ghaziabad and Delhi had good score and poor score were found for Greater Noida and Noida. The good score were found as age advances, good score prevalence was 69.8% at 6 years and 52.3 % at 3 years of age with significant difference. On sex predilection female had 64.4% good score and poor 12.1% and male had 59.1 % good score and 13.5 % poor score and difference was found to be significant.

On basis of questionnaire, it was found that parents lack attitude to follow practice through having knowledge of oral health. Among the different types of treatment required, there was urgent need of maternal education and requirement of dental treatment modalities. More of the health education programmes implementation should be done and more of awareness for oral health practices should be incremented in the society. Parents could also benefit from oral health education and should be advised regarding continuous dental follow-ups with dietary instructions to maintain good oral hygiene. It can be concluded that, mothers are responsible for their child's life-style, behavior and habits and represents the primary information about oral health. Hence, pre and postnatal counseling of mothers about oral health will help in increasing the oral health awareness of their children. If oral health promotion efforts are to be effective in improving the oral health of young children, it is essential that there be a good understanding of parental knowledge and attitudes. Such strategies may help to guide and modify current and future oral health prevention activities. As nursing caries was

significantly associated with lower parent's education, occupation and socioeconomic status of the family. Instilling the positive attitudes of the parents towards the prevention of nursing caries would reduce the prevalence at this tender age of life.

Conclusion

Epidemiology of any disease is a very helpful tool to assess the actual status of the disease among population. Diversity in population of India with respect to dental caries provides a very beautiful condition for the study of different factors associated with dental caries. However this work is a small effort towards understanding of factors associated with dental caries, but this study fails to correlate the data with other studies in this study sample population. Whilst many studies have looked for predictors of caries in young children, many have not used the optimum study design, which is a longitudinal study. There is also a shortage of high quality studies, particularly those using validated measures for dietary and oral hygiene habits. Particularly in study population sample no study is conducted so comparison could not be made. The prevalence of dental caries and its relation with various risk factors was estimated in 2000, 3-6-year-old school going children of Delhi and NCR. Following conclusions were drawn from this study.

1. The prevalence of dental caries was high in the 3-6- year-age group; with the highest prevalence seen at 3 year-age group compared to that of 5 age group.
2. Caries prevalence did not show any variation in relation to sex.
3. Oral hygiene scores in all the regions of the study were positively good.
4. A strong correlation was seen between sugar consumption and caries, with the prevalence increasing with increasing sugar exposure.
5. Caries prevalence did not have any statistically significant relation with oral hygiene habits.
6. Low maternal education was found in overall study sample with correlation of knowledge with practice, but poor correlation of practice with attitude. Overall proper attitude was been found.
7. In view of the large body of literature the review is limited to studies identified by computer searching. Hand searching of journals and gathering of unpublished reports and conference proceedings was out of scope

Overall, the findings of this survey will form part of a baseline for the oral health assessment for children below 6 years of age in Delhi and NCR, India.

From the results of this study, it can be concluded that caries prevalence in preschool children of Delhi/NCR was 28%. with a mean deft of 2.41 and mean DMFT of 0.63 and the risk factors for ECC

included age, low maternal education, low attitude towards following oral hygiene practices, improper feeding and oral hygiene habits. However, more detailed collaborative study is required to infer actual role of these associated factor in dental caries etiology. The data can be helpful for designing the preventive measures against dental caries on the basis of factors associated with it.

Results reveal an urgent need to increase awareness among the public about ECC. The establishment of “good oral health practices early in life can lead to a healthier mouth” in later years of life. For this to happen, awareness of the various oral disorders, their causes, prevention and cure must be created at the earliest available opportunity so as to install positive attitude among Mothers /Caregivers.

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